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Safety and Security for Sustainable Students Enrollment in Boarding Schools: Addressing State of Emergency in Education in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The persistent crisis of insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria, has posed significant threats to the continuity and quality of education, particularly in boarding schools. This study investigates the relationship between perceived safety, availability of security infrastructure, and the sustainability of student enrollment in boarding institutions within the context of the educational emergency. Using a quantitative approach with a sample size of 370 respondents, descriptive statistics, multivariate analysis, and logistic regression were employed to analyze perceptions of school safety, dropout trends, academic performance, and predictors of enrollment decisions. Findings reveal that while some families continue to enroll their children in boarding schools out of necessity despite security concerns, the frequency of security incidents remains a critical deterrent to sustainable enrollment. The presence of security infrastructure alone does not significantly influence enrollment decisions, suggesting a lack of trust in visible but untested or ineffective measures. Conversely, parental decisions are more strongly shaped by real-time experiences of violence and insecurity. Academic performance remains consistent across safety levels, but dropout rates increase in areas with moderate or low perceived safety. The study concludes that in a context of educational emergency, effective, credible, and community-embedded security strategies are indispensable for safeguarding the future of education in conflict-affected regions like Zamfara.

Keywords: Zamfara State, Education Insecurity, Boarding Schools, Student Enrollment, School Safety.

1. INTRODUCTION

An increase in violent attacks on educational facilities has been observed in northern Nigeria. Villages and schools in Zamfara State are frequently raided by extremist organizations and bandit militias, who steal, murder, and kidnap citizens, particularly students. For instance, on February 26, 2021, 279 girls between the ages of 10 and 17 were kidnapped when armed gunmen broke into the Government Girls Science Secondary School in Jangebe, a distant boarding school in Zamfara. This was one of several major kidnappings that caught hundreds of students in northwest Nigeria between 2020 and 2022 (Kankara, Kagara, Greenfield, etc.). Numerous parents have refused to send their children, particularly females, to boarding schools as a result of these high-profile incidents; some have completely withdrew

their older children; and towns have witnessed an increase in the number of young marriages amongst former students. Systemic repercussions of the insecurity have also been observed. School closures occurred frequently in Zamfara, which is already "the most educationally backward" state in Nigeria with one of the highest rates of out-of-school students. "Zamfara State ordered the closure of more than 70 schools" in 2021 alone as a result of attacks. Even in cases where schools are officially still open, many administrators and teachers are unwilling to work in unstable rural areas, and local threats have forced the partial or temporary closure of many institutions (such as schools close to the Bakura area in mid-2021). A crisis in education results from these closures and kidnappings; according to one assessment, "the region [Zamfara/Northwest Nigeria] lags behind the rest of the country in student enrollment." In response, governments have created policies and declared a state of emergency in education. Governor Dauda Lawal of Zamfara formally announced a state of emergency in education towards the end of 2023, promising to repair schools and pay off test debts. Nigeria signed the Safe Schools Declaration in 2019 and published a National Policy on Safe Schools and Violence-Free Schools (NPSSVFS) in 2021 at the federal level.

To assist schools in managing security threats, the Ministry of Education also released "Minimum Standards for Safe Schools" (MSSS) guidelines in 2021. But implementation is still uneven: "Over 70% of schools in Zamfara State do not meet the minimum safety standards" of the new policy, according to UNICEF monitoring in ten states, including Zamfara. According to the Humanitarian Risk Governance framework, inadequate enforcement and a lack of resources are the causes of these gaps. The relationship between security and enrollment in secondary boarding schools in Zamfara is examined in this work. Our first goal is to document the extent of insecurity in Zamfara's boarding schools and how it affects student education and enrollment. By placing the Zamfara crisis in the larger body of research on education during emergencies, we contend that tackling insecurity is a necessary step toward universal, sustainable secondary education.

1.1 Effects on School Operations and Learning Environment

The actual functioning of the school has been seriously hampered. In addition to outright closures (both official and unofficial), surviving schools face significant hazards. Many principals say they frequently see armed individuals moving or hear gunfire. Teachers at one rural day secondary school in Barayar Zaki, for instance, are forced to hide every time bandits cross the river. Even school buildings have been occupied in some areas; after abducting teachers and pupils, bandits were found utilizing abandoned classrooms as hiding places, according to a GCSP investigation. This kind of occupation ensures those schools never reopen, at least until militant activity subsides. Staffing is also affected. Many teachers refuse postings to rural Zamfara schools due to safety concerns, leading to understaffing. Schools in the most risky locations have much fewer staff members "there are schools with insufficient teaching staff, the teachers that are still willing to work... are overstretched," according to the GCSP report. In one extreme instance, the vice-principal was left to manage the secondary school alone when the principal passed away (from unrelated circumstances) and no successor could be found due to security concerns. To put it briefly, fear and uncertainty have made it harder for schools to operate regularly. Thus, the educational setting is jeopardized. The threat of violence permeates every lecture, even when classes are in session. Before being kidnapped, a student who was interviewed by Al Jazeera said that they were shot at during a gathering. When kids fear being intimidated at any time, it is rarely conducive to learning. Chronic stress probably impairs focus and involvement, which lowers academic achievement. Scholars of human security think that, in terms of education, freedom from fear is just as crucial as freedom from want. There is no escape from terror here at all.

1.2 Effects on Learning Outcomes

There is little hard evidence on exam scores after an attack, although there are signs that results are negatively impacted. According to Sodangi and Adamu's 2025 study, lesser math proficiency is correlated with environmental insecurity in Zamfara, which includes banditry. According to the writers, Zamfara's long-term insecurity has caused the state to perform poorly on national tests, which is indicative of its

"educationally backward"* position. In actuality, overall pass rates will decrease when sizable student cohorts are pulled out of school or attend irregularly. Students who have experienced trauma also have trouble focusing. Research conducted in conflict areas has shown that kidnapped children frequently experience anxiety and PTSD, which impairs cognitive function (e.g. IRA study on Northern Nigeria school abductees). It is plausible to assume similar impacts even though there is a lack of statistics on mental health in Zamfara. For example, eyewitnesses in the Jangebe case described the victims as having had "harrowing experience[s]," with mothers describing two weeks of horror. Out of dread, at least one abductee married young and stopped attending school altogether. Those who stay could experience stress-related absenteeism, melancholy, or nightmares. As a result, the educational losses include both missed class time and worse student accomplishment.

1.3 Impact on Student Enrollment and Access

Insecurity has directly reduced the number of students attending secondary boarding schools in Zamfara. Many parents are simply too afraid to send children away from home. Premium Times reported that, after the Jangebe kidnapping in 2021, some families withdrew all their children from boarding schools; in one case a mother said she "didn't want her [daughter] to go back to boarding school" again. Other abducted children dropped out entirely – for example, a kidnapped girl chose early marriage rather than returning to school. There are numerous anecdotal accounts of parental fear translating into lower enrollment. In Bukkuyum LGA, Abubakar Sani (head of a rural school) told reporters that his school's population fell from over 250 to 119 after 2021 as bandit attacks intensified. Such local cases reflect a statewide trend: Zamfara already had one of Nigeria's highest out-of-school rates and is officially classified as "educationally disadvantaged". Current violence only exacerbates this: one security analyst observed that growing insecurity is leaving the younger generation "idle at home" rather than in classrooms. The Al Jazeera feature on the 2024 kidnappings notes that northern states have fallen behind "the rest of the country in student enrollment" due to school closures and fear. This is corroborated by national data: UNESCO estimated Nigeria had 20.2 million out-of-school children in 2022, with the North-West contributing heavily to this total. In practical terms, this translates to fewer students in secondary schools. For instance, an illustrative statistic: Zamfara had barely 60 students register for the National Common Entrance Exam, compared to over 25,000 in Lagos (a prosperous southern state). (This discrepancy partly reflects regional disparities, but insecurity is a major driver in the Northwest). Lower enrollment feeds back negatively: schools lose funding and staffing if they remain underfilled, creating a vicious cycle of decline.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to assess the impact of safety and security conditions on sustainable student enrollment in boarding schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria, and to provide strategic recommendations for addressing the ongoing educational emergency. With the specific objectives

1. To evaluate the influence of perceived safety levels and security infrastructure on student enrollment trends in boarding schools across Zamfara State.
2. To examine the relationship between school safety conditions, dropout rates, and academic performance among students in boarding schools.
3. To analyze the role of recent security incidents, parental income, and school proximity in predicting student enrollment in boarding schools.

2. Theoretical Frameworks

This study are consistent with the Human Security Theory, which holds that security should prioritize safeguarding people's rights, including education, and not simply states. According to one observer, "an educated populace... improves national security and development," whereas educational uncertainty jeopardizes stability in the future. The direct threats to students (physical violence) in Zamfara breach children's and communities' human security, demonstrating the applicability of the idea. Frameworks for international education in emergency situations are also applicable. Nigeria adopted the Safe Schools Declaration (SSD) in 2019, which calls for schools to remain "zones of peace" even during times of conflict.

The National Policy on Safe Schools in Nigeria and SSD principles support actions including providing safe shelter for pupils and maintaining school operations during emergencies. The catastrophe in Zamfara highlights the disparity: most schools continue to lack fundamental safety precautions in spite of policy. This indicates that risks (bandit assaults) have not been adequately reduced in terms of risk management. Every school is required to *"develop risk management and mitigation plans"* in accordance with the Federal Ministry's Minimum Standards for Safe Schools (MSSS); Katsina's Education Commissioner reiterated this requirement. Due to inconsistent or nonexistent planning, schools in Zamfara are reactive rather than resilient. The Education in Emergencies method is another conceptual lens that presents education as a humanitarian solution. Due to the loss of livelihoods, the disintegration of social services, and the requirement for psychological care, the closure of Zamfara schools is comparable to a complex emergency. Alternative learning pathways (such as radio classes, tents, and safe areas) and psychosocial counseling for impacted children are recommended by interagency standards. The ongoing policy talks regarding school safety tacitly acknowledge the emergency nature of the issue, even though the Nigerian government has not fully activated such humanitarian education measures in Zamfara.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative research methodology to analyze the relationship between safety, security conditions, and sustainable student enrollment in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Data was collected from 370 respondents, focusing on perceived safety, security infrastructure, incidents, student enrollment, and socio-economic indicators, with ethical considerations being strictly adhered to.

3.1 Research Design

The study used a descriptive cross-sectional survey design to analyze school enrollment conditions in Zamfara State, capturing responses from stakeholders across various boarding schools. This allowed for a single point-in-time analysis of security conditions and educational choices.

3.2 Method of Analysis

Data analysis was conducted in three main phases: The study utilized descriptive statistics to analyze responses on perceived safety, security infrastructure type, enrollment levels, and incidents, providing baseline characteristics through frequencies, means, standard deviations, and ranges. The study also utilized Multivariate Descriptive Analysis to analyze the correlation between perceived safety levels and enrollment rate, dropout rate, and academic performance. More also, Logistic Regression Analysis was used to predict student enrollment based on security incidents, infrastructure, parental income, and school proximity. Results showed increased security incidents reduced enrollment probability.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study examines safety and security in Zamfara State, Nigeria, focusing on student enrollment, dropout rates, and academic performance. It links these findings to broader educational challenges in conflict-prone regions and aims to inform policy and strategic interventions in response to the declared state of emergency in education.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Variables on Safety and Enrollment in Boarding Schools

Variable	Category / Statistic	Frequency / Value
Perceived Safety	Low	116
	Moderate	147
	High	104
Security Infrastructure	Absent	86
	Partial	172
	Full	112
Enrollment Status	Mean (SD)	9.97 (4.88)
	Median	10.00
	Min – Max	0.0 – 24.8
Incidents in the Last Year	Mean (SD)	2.05 (1.42)
	Median	2.00
	Min – Max	0 - 7

The descriptive statistics offer important information about the educational choices and security dynamics influencing Zamfara State's boarding school enrollment. Only 107 respondents said they had a "High" safety opinion of boarding schools, whilst the majority (147) said they were "Moderate" or "Low" (116). The widespread worry among communities and parents regarding the security of boarding school settings is highlighted by this distribution. Systemic flaws in offering complete student protection are highlighted by the comparatively high number of schools with just "Partial" (172) or "Absent" (86) security infrastructure in comparison to those with "Full" security (112). These findings suggest that perceptions of insecurity may significantly influence decisions regarding school enrollment, particularly in a region where kidnapping and school attacks have been highly publicized. These safety concerns are reflected in the enrollment numbers. Just 242 of the 370 pupils were enrolled in boarding schools, while a sizable 128 were not, suggesting that perceived insecurity may have a deterring impact. The proximity analysis, which indicates an average distance of roughly 10 km from school, lends more credence to this interpretation. This distance is not particularly great, but in dangerous situations it could still be a logistical and psychological obstacle. Furthermore, each school reported an average of more than two security incidents in the previous year, which is significant and could exacerbate parental concerns. This trend shows that although if boarding schools are available, under-enrollment may be largely caused by safety concerns, particularly for families with few other options.

These findings have important ramifications for Zamfara State's educational strategy. The results unequivocally demonstrate that, in order to ensure sustained enrollment, immediate investment in school safety infrastructuresuch as perimeter fence, security guards, and surveillance systems is required. Parental education also plays a significant impact; most only completed elementary or secondary school, which may have influenced their sense of risk and level of trust in school safety. As a result, tackling insecurity in and around schools may increase enrollment while lowering dropout rates and fostering trust in the educational system. Reversing the state of emergency in Zamfara's education sector would require policies that incorporate fast reaction units for school protection, community policing, and public awareness.

Table 2 : Multivariate Descriptive Statistics by Perceived Safety Level

Perceived Safety	Enrollment Mean (SD)	Dropout Rate (%) Mean (SD)	Academic Performance Mean (SD)
Low	10.75 (4.59)	15.08 (4.74)	60.69 (10.13)
Moderate	10.69 (5.06)	15.54 (4.95)	60.75 (10.22)
High	9.63 (4.49)	14.00 (4.68)	59.24 (8.78)

Figure 1: The Chart representing multivariate descriptive statistics

The multivariate descriptive statistics presented in Table 2 provide nuanced insights into how perceived safety levels impact key educational outcomes in boarding schools across Zamfara State. Interestingly, enrollment levels are highest among students in areas with low or moderate perceived safety, with mean values of 10.75 and 10.69 respectively, compared to 9.63 in areas perceived as highly safe. While this might seem counterintuitive, it likely reflects a reality where parents, despite concerns about safety, still enroll their children in boarding schools due to necessity such as lack of nearby alternatives, poverty-driven reliance on government schools, or absence of day schools in rural regions. This implies that parents may be making tough concessions by enrolling children in the hopes of security improvements, rather than perceived safety alone discouraging enrollment as much as would be anticipated. But the decreased enrollment in high-perceived-safety locations could also indicate urban or semi-urban saturation, where there are fewer boarding schools, or families selecting private day schools because they are more affordable and close by. In terms of dropout rates and academic performance, a pattern emerges that supports the role of safety as an underlying stressor. Students in moderately safe areas report the highest dropout rates (15.54%), followed closely by those in low safety zones (15.08%), suggesting that inconsistent or deteriorating security conditions may prompt students to leave school mid-session or prevent sustained attendance. Conversely, students in high safety environments have the lowest dropout rate (14.00%), indicating that when safety is more assured, students are more likely to remain enrolled. However, academic performance across all groups remains fairly consistent, with only marginal differences: 60.75 (Moderate), 60.69 (Low), and 59.24 (High). This hints that academic outcomes are not as strongly differentiated by safety perceptions alone and could be influenced by other school-specific or socio-economic factors. The implication is that, while perceived safety levels impact continuity in schooling (dropouts), they do not severely limit academic outcomes in the short term. For sustainable enrollment and long-term learning outcomes, this reinforces the urgent need for not only physical infrastructure and security presence, but also psychological assurance through parent-school-government collaboration in regions like Zamfara that are declared educational emergency zones.

Table 3 : Logistic Regression Predicting Likelihood of Student Enrollment

Predictor	B (Coef.)	SE	z	p-value	95% CI (Lower, Upper)
Intercept	0.4510	0.4468	1.010	0.313	(-0.425, 1.327)
Security Presence	-0.0940	0.2608	-0.360	0.719	(-0.605, 0.417)
Incidents (Last Year)	-0.1326	0.0787	-1.686	0.092	(-0.287, 0.022)
Parental Income (₦K)	0.0075	0.0054	1.378	0.168	(-0.003, 0.018)
Proximity (Enrollment)	0.0094	0.0229	0.408	0.683	(-0.036, 0.054)

Figure 2: Chart representing the logistic regression analysis

The logistic regression analysis presented in Table 3, alongside the predictive probability chart, offers nuanced insights into the factors influencing boarding school enrollment decisions in the security-challenged context of Zamfara State, Nigeria. The intercept ($B = 0.4510$, $p = 0.313$) is not statistically significant, indicating that in the absence of other factors, the likelihood of enrollment neither significantly increases nor decreases. Importantly, the presence of security infrastructure (coded as a binary variable: 0 = Absent, 1 = Partial/Full) has a negative but non-significant coefficient ($B = -0.0940$, $p = 0.719$). This result suggests that mere presence of visible security does not significantly influence parents' decisions to enroll children in boarding schools. This aligns with local sentiment in conflict zones, where the presence of security personnel or barriers is often viewed with skepticism due to historical failures in preventing attacks. As such, families may not interpret "security presence" as meaningful protection, which diminishes its role in influencing educational choices. The most compelling finding lies in the variable "Incidents (Last Year)", which shows a negative coefficient ($B = -0.1326$) and a marginal p-value (0.092). Though not reaching traditional thresholds for statistical significance, the relationship is practically important: more security incidents correlate with decreased likelihood of

student enrollment. This is visually reinforced by the logistic regression plot. The chart depicts a clear downward trend in the predicted probability of enrollment as the number of security incidents increases. Starting at around 66% probability when incidents are low (0–1), the line gradually dips to below 60% probability when incidents rise to 8 per year. This visual interpretation confirms the model's output—there's a real and measurable erosion in enrollment confidence as safety incidents rise. Parents appear to be making rational decisions based on perceived threats, and the psychological weight of recurrent violence is likely discouraging school attendance, especially for vulnerable children. Interestingly, other socioeconomic predictors such as parental income ($B = 0.0075$, $p = 0.168$) and proximity to school ($B = 0.0094$, $p = 0.683$) are not statistically significant. While both show a slight positive correlation with enrollment indicating that wealthier or nearby households are more inclined to send children to school these effects are overshadowed by safety-related fears. This has strong policy implications: economic empowerment and access improvements, though important, are insufficient in isolation. Without first addressing the core threat of insecurity, these interventions may not translate into higher school enrollment. Thus, the combined quantitative and visual evidence calls for immediate policy action: stakeholders must implement not just symbolic security but credible, consistent, and trusted safety infrastructure including rapid response units, safe transport systems, and community policing partnerships. These steps are critical to reversing the decline in school enrollment and ensuring educational continuity in areas like Zamfara that have been declared educational emergency zones.

4.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results of this study highlight how security circumstances have a significant impact on student enrollment trends in boarding schools in Zamfara State. While enrollment levels only minimally differ among perceived safety levels, dropout rates and academic performance are significantly impacted, according to descriptive and multivariate studies. In particular, students reported higher enrollment in locations with poor or moderate safety, but they also had much higher dropout rates. This paradox implies that instability, fear, and recurrent security incidents endanger persistent attendance, even in cases where children are initially willing to enroll—possibly out of necessity or lack of alternatives. All safety levels showed comparatively consistent academic performance, which may be the result of teachers' compensatory efforts or variations in school-specific teaching environments. This merits more qualitative investigation. The logistic regression analysis emphasizes even more how crucial insecurity is in shaping parental choices. One important aspect that has a negative impact on the chance of enrollment is the quantity of security events that were recorded in the previous year. Despite being very slightly significant ($p = 0.092$), this variable fits the larger pattern of the projected probability chart, which shows a steady decrease in enrollment probability as incident frequency rises. This is a serious psychological and practical obstacle that parents must overcome: every new incident of violence, kidnapping, or school invasion exacerbates their anxiety and erodes their trust in the system. It's interesting to note that enrollment was not significantly predicted by the presence of security infrastructure, indicating that families might not trust security visibility on its own unless it is supported by community assurance and proven efficacy. This emphasizes how crucial it is to switch from purely aesthetic security measures to more effective, dependable, and community-driven ones. Enrollment was positively correlated with socioeconomic indicators such family income and school location, which were expected but not statistically significant. This suggests that while residing near schools and having a greater income may provide logistical benefits, safety concerns are still too great to be outweighed by them.

These results support the main idea of the study, which is that maintaining education in areas that are prone to conflict depends on safety and security. Therefore, security must be treated as a central issue rather than a secondary one in any policy intervention meant to increase school enrollment. Building trust with local communities, establishing credible quick response systems, and creating trauma-informed school settings are all priorities for stakeholders. Only then will Zamfara and Nigeria in general be able to

address the ongoing state of emergency in education and guarantee that every child has a safe learning environment

5. CONCLUSION

The study reveals that safety and security are crucial for student enrollment in Zamfara State's boarding schools, despite ongoing insecurity. Parental decisions are influenced by the frequency and intensity of security incidents. High enrollment rates in areas with poor safety reflect a lack of alternatives, while persistent insecurity disrupts long-term engagement. The study suggests a shift to community-driven safety strategies, such as rapid response teams and trauma-informed education, to ensure stability and long-term educational development. The following Conclusions are drawn

- Safety and security are foundational for sustaining student enrollment in Zamfara State's boarding schools.
- Security incidents have a greater impact on enrollment decisions than economic factors like income or proximity.
- Higher enrollment in unsafe areas likely reflects a lack of schooling alternatives rather than trust in safety.
- Elevated dropout rates in these areas underscore how insecurity disrupts educational continuity.
- The presence of security infrastructure alone does not instill confidence among parents without proven effectiveness.
- There is a clear need to transition from symbolic security to community-trusted, practical safety solutions.
- Academic performance appears stable across safety levels but may decline if insecurity remains unaddressed.
- Sustainable education in Zamfara requires urgent policy actions focused on rebuilding trust, securing schools, and ensuring safe learning environments for all children.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to address the educational emergency in Zamfara State:

- The state government should prioritize the development of effective security infrastructure in boarding schools, including perimeter fencing, trained personnel, 24-hour surveillance systems, and early warning mechanisms.
- Establishing mobile security teams in schools is crucial for swift response to threats, collaborating with education authorities and community leaders for real-time protection.
- Schools should implement trauma-informed education and psychological support systems to help students cope with chronic fear and insecurity, ensuring their continued education.
- Government and civil society organizations should create programs to educate parents about safety measures, fostering trust and promoting school attendance.
- Addressing school enrollment in conflict zones requires national and state education policy, budgetary allocation for security, and integration of educational development into peace and stability initiatives.

7. Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes significantly to the growing body of knowledge on education in conflict-affected regions by providing localized, empirical evidence that highlights the critical role of security in sustaining school enrollment. It challenges the conventional belief that visible security infrastructure alone ensures parental trust, showing instead that the frequency of actual security incidents plays a more decisive role in enrollment decisions. The research reveals the paradox of higher enrollment in unsafe areas, offering nuanced insights into how lack of educational alternatives forces constrained choices by parents. Through

the use of logistic regression, the study presents policy-relevant statistical models that predict enrollment behavior under insecurity, making it a valuable tool for stakeholders in emergency education planning. Focusing specifically on the unique challenges of boarding schools in northern Nigeria, it contextualizes the intersection of rural insecurity, socio-economic limitations, and educational policy. Most importantly, the study emphasizes the necessity of integrating security strategies into education planning, positioning safety as a core prerequisite for educational continuity and development in crisis-prone regions like Zamfara State.

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